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IEEE FNTC* Role in Driving IEEE 6G Standardization

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*Future Networks Technical Community

Technology -> Standards -> Product -> Market

- ✓ Technologies alone does not mean success!
- ✓ Customer/user need: outside-in
- ✓ Market opportunity: utility, cost, barrier to entry, IP
- ✓ Standards and building to standards a must to be successful, but not easily done! **But, open standards is the new way forward!!**

Why standards?

- **Rapid Reaction Standardization Activities (RRSA)**
- **Project Authorization Request (PAR)**

Future Networks Technical Community

(A graduated initiative of Future Directions)

ORG STRUCTURE

Current Chair
Fawzi Behmann

Vice Chair
Tim Lee

Past Chair
Ashutosh Dutta

Staff
Craig Polk

MILESTONES

- 2017 Founding
- 2018 1st event
- 2019 1st roadmap
- 2021 CTU
- 2022 Testbed
- 2023 graduation

STANDARDS

- 3 programs
- 2 PARs

Steering Committee | 2 Subcommittees | 7 Committees | 15 Tech Working Group | +2k active participants

9 Sponsor Societies

Lead Sponsor

Major Sponsors

Content

IEEE Future Networks Tech Focus Issue 16, June 2023 + webinars, newsletter, podcasts, videos, articles

3 Major Events

Research & Education

IEEE INGR International Network Generations Roadmap + eLearning, distinguished lectures, webinar series, white papers, tutorials

futurenetworks.ieee.org | fnwf.ieee.org | ctu.ieee.org

IEEE INGR Structure and Working Groups

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	INGR WORKING GROUP CHAPTERS
User Access	This category describes how the users reach the network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Satellites Deployment Connecting the Unconnected (CTU)
Network Components and Performance	This category describes how the networks are interconnected	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Edge Services & Automation Massive MIMO System Optimization Optics mmWave Quantum Information Technologies (QIT) (new in 2024)
Systems and Standards	This category describes system standards and testability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standardization Building Blocks (SBB) Testbed Energy Efficiency
Services and Enablers	This category represents all the elements that enable deployment, assure functionality and security and address impact on society and environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Security Applications and Services Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning (AI/ML)

**14 Chapters
(2023 Edition)**

<https://futurenetworks.ieee.org/roadmap>

IEEE Governance

IEEE Standards Association

IEEE Standards Committees

Responsible for the development and maintenance of standards shall be one of the following:

IEEE Standards Development Groups

IEEE Standards Development Process

IEEE standards are classified as:

Standards

- Documents with mandatory requirements
- “Shall” indicates mandatory requirements to be strictly followed without deviation in order to conform to the standard

Recommended practices

- Documents in which procedures and positions preferred by the IEEE are presented
- “Should” indicates a particular recommendation among several possibilities without mentioning or excluding others; or that a certain course of action is preferred but not necessarily required

Guides

- Documents in which alternate approaches to good practice are suggested but no clear-cut recommendations are made
- “May” indicates a course of actions permissible within the limits of a standard
- “Can” indicates possibility and capability

Trial-Use documents

- Publications in effect for not more than three years. They can be any of the categories; standards, recommended practices or guides.
- A draft is usually considered for trial-use status when:
 - The WG feels draft needs input from a broader constituency;
 - The Standards Committee is unable to resolve negative ballots to a satisfactory level, or
 - When the SASB cannot attain a suitable level of approval for a draft submitted for adoption as an IEEE Standard.

Types of Standards Projects

Principles of Standards Development

-
- 1 Direct Participation
 - 2 Due Process
 - 3 Broad Consensus
 - 4 Balance
 - 5 Broad Openness
 - 6 Coherence
 - 7 Development Dimension
 - 8 Transparency

Standards Development Lifecycle

IEEE: Standards and Global Collaboration for 5G & Beyond

IEEE provides a complete, end-to-end, collaborative framework today for accelerating the realization of 5G and B5G and its revolutionary use cases tomorrow.

Mobile Edge Cloud brings SDN/NFV frameworks and data path programmability to the proximity of end users as key enablers for service differentiation

IEEE 802.11
standard supported by almost any mobile device in the market today

SoftRAN is to create a SD RAN flexible enough to control applications with the wireline centric concepts of "fog" in a SD-controller

IEEE 1914/1904
flexible, efficient and scalable packet-based fronthaul transport networks

IEEE P1589/P1587.6/P1857.9/P3333.2.4 Industry Connections
the integration of computer-generated sensory content with the physical world

IEEE 1918
non/mision-critical applications (e.g. manufacturing, transportation, healthcare, mobility, edutainment, events)

IEEE 11073
provides a global platform for eHealth stakeholders

IEEE P2413 / 1471 / 42010

Rapid Reaction Standardization Activities (RRSA) Process Flow

PAR – Project Authorization Request

5G and Future Networks Related IEEE Standards Timeline

IEEE Emerging Technologies Standardization Activities

Virtualized and Software Defined Networks and Services

Approved Standards:

- IEEE 1903-2011: IEEE Standard for the Functional Architecture of Next Generation Service Overlay Networks (NGSON)
- IEEE 1903.1-2017: IEEE Approved Draft Standard for Content Delivery Protocols of Next Generation Service Overlay Network
- IEEE 1903.2-2017: IEEE Approved Draft Standard for Service Composition Protocols of Next Generation Service Overlay Network (NGSON)
- IEEE 1903.3-2017: IEEE Approved Draft Standard for Self-Organizing Management Protocols of Next Generation Service Overlay Network
- IEEE 1930.1-2022: Recommended Practice for Software Defined Networking (SDN) Based Middleware for Control and Management of Wireless Networks
- IEEE 1906.1-2015: IEEE Recommended Practice for Nanoscale and Molecular Communication Framework

IEEE Emerging Technologies Standardization Activities

Active Projects:

- P1913: Software-Defined Quantum Communication
- P1916.1: Standard for Software Defined Networking and Network Function Virtualization Performance
- P1938.1: Standard for Software Defined Protocol and Functional Requirements for Improvement of the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) in Communications Channels
- P1950.1: Standard for Communications Architectural Functional Framework for Smart Cities
- P1951.1: Standard for Discovering and Intent Sharing between Smart City Component Systems
- P2784: Guide for the Technology and Process Framework for Planning a Smart City
- P1952: Resilient Positioning, Navigation, And Timing User Equipment
- P1943.1: Standard for Post-Quantum Network Security

IEEE Emerging Technologies Standardization Activities

Green ICT

Approved Standards:

- IEEE 1923.1-2021: IEEE Standard for Computation of Energy Efficiency Upper Bound for Apparatus Processing Communication Signal Waveforms
- IEEE 1924.1-2022: IEEE Recommended Practice for developing energy efficient power-proportional digital architectures

IEEE Emerging Technologies Standardization Activities

Active Projects:

- P1922.1: A method for calculating anticipated emissions caused by virtual machine migration and placement
- P1922.2: A method to calculate near real-time emissions of information and communication technology infrastructure
- P1925.1: Energy Efficient Dynamic Line Rate Transmission System
- P1926.1: A Functional Architecture of Distributed Energy Efficient Big Data Processing
- P1927.1: Services Provided by the Energy-Efficient Orchestration and Management of Virtualized Distributed Data Centers Interconnected by a Virtualized Network
- P1928.1: A Mechanism for Energy Efficient Virtual Machine Placement
- P1929.1: An Architectural Framework for Energy Efficient Content Distribution

IEEE Emerging Technologies Standardization Activities

Mobile Communication Networks

Approved Standards:

- IEEE 1914.3-2018: IEEE Standard for Radio over Ethernet Encapsulations and Mappings
- IEEE 1914.1-2019: IEEE Standard for Packet-based Front-Haul Transport Networks
- IEEE P1918.1: Tactile Internet: Application Scenarios, Definitions and Terminology, Architecture, Functions, and Technical Assumptions

Active Projects:

- P1918.1: Tactile Internet: Application Scenarios, Definitions and Terminology, Architecture, Functions, and Technical Assumptions
- P1918.1.1: Haptic Codecs for the Tactile Internet
- P1920.1: Aerial Communications and Networking Standards
- P1931.1: An Architectural Framework for Real-time Onsite Operations Facilitation (ROOF) for the Internet of Things
- P1932.1: Licensed / Unlicensed Spectrum Interoperability in Wireless Mobile Networks
- P2061: Architecture for Low-Mobility Energy-Efficient Network for Affordable Broadband Access

IEEE Emerging Technologies Standardization Activities

Access and Core Networks

Active Projects:

- P1942.1: Standard for Massive Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) Architectural Framework IEEE 1910.1-2020 - IEEE Standard for Meshed Tree Bridging with Loop-Free Forwarding

IEEE Emerging Technologies Standardization Activities

Edge, Fog, Cloud Communications with IOT and Big Data

Approved Standards:

- IEEE 1906.1-2015: IEEE Recommended Practice for Nanoscale and Molecular Communication Framework
- IEEE 1906.1.1-2020: Standard Data Model for Nanoscale Communication Systems
- IEEE 1934-2018: OpenFog Reference Architecture for Fog Computing
- IEEE 2410-2017: IEEE Standard for Biometrics Open Protocol Standard

Active Projects:

- P1912: Privacy and Security Architecture for Consumer Wireless Devices
- P1934.1: Nomenclature and Taxonomy for Distributing Computing, Communications and Networking along the Things-to-Cloud Continuum
- P1935: Standard for Edge / Fog Manageability and Orchestration

Thank You!

Kittos!

Tak!

Merci!

Danke Schön!

Gracias!

Ciao!

धन्यवाद!

□ □ !

Join IEEE FNTC to drive B5G Standards

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